

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 75

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 75

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 75:0 For the choir director; <i>set to</i> †Al-tashheth. A Psalm of Asaph, a Song.</p>	<p>Psa. 75:1 לְמִנְצַחַת אֶל-תְּשִׁיחַת</p>
<p>Psa. 75:1 We ^agive thanks to You, O God, we give thanks, For Your name is ^bnear; Men declare ^cYour wondrous works. ² “When I select an ^aappointed time, It is I who ^bjudge with equity. ³ “The ^aearth and all who dwell in it ¹melt; It is I who have firmly set its ^bpillars. ²Selah. ⁴ “I said to the boastful, ‘Do not boast,’ And to the wicked, “Do not lift up the horn; ⁵ Do not lift up your horn on high, “Do not speak with insolent ¹pride.”</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר לְאַסָּף שִׁיר : ² הוֹדִינוּ לָךְ אֱלֹהִים הוֹדִינוּ וְקָרֹב שְׁמֶךָ סִפְרוּ נִבְלֹאוֹתֶיךָ : ³ כִּי אֶקַּח מוֹעֵד אֲנִי מִיִּשְׁרָיִם אֲשַׁפֵּט : ⁴ נִמְגִים אֶרֶץ וְכָל-יֹשְׁבֵיהָ אֲנֹכִי תִכְנַתִּי עַמּוּדֵיהָ סֵלָה : ⁵ אֶמְרָתִי לְהוֹלִלִים אֶל-תִּהְיוּ וְלִרְשָׁעִים אֶל-תִּרְימוּ קֶרֶן : ⁶ אֶל-תִּרְימוּ לְמָרוֹם קַרְנֵכֶם תִּדְבְּרוּ בְצוֹנָאֵר עָתָק : ⁷ כִּי לֹא מִמּוֹצָא וּמִמַּעַרְב וְלֹא מִמִּדְבַּר הַרְרִים : ⁸ כִּי-אֱלֹהִים שֹׁפֵט זֶה יִשְׁפִּיל וְזֶה יָרִים : ⁹ כִּי כּוֹס בְּיַד-יְהוָה וַיִּזַּן חֲמַר אֶמְלֵא מִסֶּךָ וַיִּגַּר מִיָּדָה אֶד-שְׁמָרְיָה יִמְצוּ יִשְׁתּוּ כָּל-רְשָׁעֵי-אֶרֶץ : ¹⁰ וְאֲנִי אֲנִיד</p>
<p>Psa. 75:6 For not from the east, nor from the west, Nor from the ^{1a}desert <i>comes</i> exaltation; ⁷ But ^aGod is the Judge; He ^bputs down one and exalts another. ⁸ For a ^acup is in the hand of the LORD, and the wine foams; It is ^{1b}well mixed, and He pours out of this; Surely all the wicked of the earth must drain <i>and</i> ^cdrink down its dregs.</p>	

Psa. 75:9 But as for me, I will ^adeclare *it* forever;

I will sing praises to the God of Jacob.

¹⁰ And all the ^ahorns of the wicked

¹He will cut off,

But ^bthe horns of the righteous will be lifted up.

לְעַלְמֵי אֲזִמְזָה לֵאלֹהֵי
יַעֲקֹב׃ 11 וְכָל-קַרְנֵי רָשָׁעִים
אֲגַדֵּעַ תְּרוֹמְמָה קַרְנוֹת
צַדִּיק׃

References

Psalm 75:0

[†]Lit *Do Not Destroy*

Psalm 75:1

^aPs 79:13

^bPs 145:18

^cPs 26:7; 44:1; 71:17

Psalm 75:2

^aPs 102:13

^bPs 9:8; 67:4; Is 11:4

Psalm 75:3

¹Or *totter*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 46:6; Is 24:19

^{b1} Sam 2:8

Psalm 75:4

^aZech 1:21

Psalm 75:5

¹Lit *neck*

^{a1} Sam 2:3; Ps 94:4

Psalm 75:6

¹Or *mountainous desert*

^aPs 3:3

Psalm 75:7

^aPs 50:6

^{b1} Sam 2:7; Ps 147:6; Dan 2:21

Psalm 75:8

¹Lit *full of mixture*

^aJob 21:20; Ps 11:6; 60:3; Jer 25:15

^bProv 23:30

^cObad 16

Psalm 75:9

^aPs 22:22; 40:10

Psalm 75:10

¹Heb *I*

^aPs 101:8; Jer 48:25

^{b1} Sam 2:1; Ps 89:17; 92:10; 148:14

Targum

Psa. 75:1 For praise; in the time that David said, “Do not harm your people.” A psalm composed by Asaph, and a song. ² We have praised you, O LORD, we have praised you, and your name is near, your wonders have declared it. ³ Because of the meeting of the festival, I will judge uprightly. ⁴ The inhabitants of the earth melt away, and all who dwell in it; I have made its pillars firm forever. ⁵ I said to the mockers, “Do not mock,” and to the wicked, “Do not exalt [your] honor.” ⁶ Do not exalt your honor to the height, you who speak in harshness and blasphemy. ⁷ For there is none beside me from east to west, nor from the north, the area of deserts, to the south, the site of mountains. ⁸ For God is a righteous judge; this one he will humble, and this one he will exalt. ⁹ For the cup of cursing is in the hand of the LORD, and a harsh wine, full of a bitter mixture, to confuse the wits of the wicked by what is poured out from it, and more severe than the judgment of the ancients; yet its dregs and its foam all the wicked of the earth will press out and drink. ¹⁰ But I will tell forever the miracles; I will praise the God of Jacob. ¹¹ But all the mighty loftiness of the wicked I will humble; I will uproot them from their strongholds; the mighty loftiness of the righteous will be magnified.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

Even though the Babylonian Exile did come to a close, many Hebrew people lived outside the Promised Land. This situation is considered an exile for the Jewish people. The problems for Israel are going to mount in rapid succession. At the end of time, a battle between Gog and Magog will encompass the globe. Trampled and terrified, Israel will turn to the LORD for salvation. The LORD will respond with the assurance that salvation is imminent. It is the LORD who will decide when the waiting time for the restoration of Israel will occur.

Verse one

The Psalmist calls out to the Sefirah Netzach to grant victory for Israel when the destruction of the world comes.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. Stop the destruction of the world. A psalm, a song of Asaf.

Verse two

Human greatness consists of two concepts. The first is the “hand” with which humans rule over the earth. The second is “perception,” which is the power in the spiritual sense of the word.

We have rendered You homage, O God, we have rendered homage, and Your name is near to us still; Your wondrous works have recounted it.

Verse four

Even though the earth and all its inhabitants' despair, I have established its pillars with deliberation. Meditate on this verse.

Verse six

Suppose you set yourself above your fellow person because of your contempt for the Torah. In that case, you set yourself above the LORD by presuming to despise Him and trample His Law underfoot.

Metaphorical translation - Lift not your horn heavenward by speaking insolence with a haughty neck.

Spiritual translation – Do not let yourself be in contempt of the Torah because you are showing hatred for the LORD.

Verse nine

When the LORD determines a person's fate, He considers not only his past or present but, most of all, his future needs.

Metaphorical translation - For there is a cup in the hand of God, the wine has ceased to ferment, but it is full of a mixture when He pours out from it. All the lawless of the earth shall drain and drink only the dregs.

Spiritual translation - When the LORD determines a person's fate, He takes into account not only his past or present but also his future needs.

Verse ten

The righteous will be rewarded, and the wicked will get what they deserve.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

